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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

D2.2 TCM Separation Process

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
DES	Deep Eutectic Solvent
US	Ultrasound
TCMs	Technology Critical Metals
PV	Photovoltaic
ChCl	Choline Chloride
EG	Ethylene Glycol
DI	Deionized
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
EDX	Energy Dispersive X-ray
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
3DM	Deep Decomposition and Deconvolution Microscopy
Ag	Silver
Al	Aluminium
Cu	Copper
Fe	Iron
Ca	Calcium
Na	Sodium
Si	Silicon
TA1-FB	Time Analysis-Sample 1-FeCl ₃ in Brine
TA1-CB	Time Analysis-Sample 1-CuCl ₂ in Brine
TAU1-FB	Time Analysis-Ultra-sonification-Sample 1-FeCl ₃ in Brine
TAU1-CE	Time Analysis-Ultra-sonification-Sample 1-CuCl ₂ in Ethaline

1. Executive Summary

The APOLLO project has made significant progress in advancing innovative etching techniques through the integration of sonification processes in deep eutectic solvent (DES) media. In D2.2, our primary focus has been on the comparative analysis of etching rates between ultrasonication and conventional stirring methods, particularly for silver (Ag). In addition to this, other necessary identification related to the metal composition and their requisite surface characterizations have been performed. The initial experiments related to extraction of Ag has also been performed by various methods outlined in this report.

Key achievements include the optimization of ultrasonication parameters, which demonstrated enhanced etching efficiency and improved uniformity in metal dissolution. Our studies confirmed that sonification significantly accelerates the Ag etching process compared to traditional stirring by promoting mass transport and enhancing surface interactions.

2. Planned Criteria

This report presents the processing and analysis of shredded samples received from CSP Fraunhofer (that has been mechanically processed as mentioned in Deliverable D2.1), utilizing sonification techniques to optimize Deep Eutectic Solvent (DES) and Ultrasound (US) for recovering Technology Critical Metals (TCMs) from photovoltaic (PV) modules. Detailed experimental methodologies, results, and conclusions are provided, supporting the execution of the Planned Pilot Plant.

3. Chemical Processing of Shredded Samples

3.1 Materials and Methods

3.1.1 Samples

Shredded PV modules labelled as APOLLO_A31_CSP_01-02-24. UoL received two sizes of these shredded samples from CSP. One Coarse sample with size 0.05 mm to 1.0 mm (**Figure 1**) and another fine powder with size <0.05 mm. While both the sample sizes have been analysed and processed further for metals recovery, the prime focus of this work has been on the coarse Sample 1. Sized between 0.05 mm to 1.00 mm. Therefore, in this report, the coarse sample will be referred as **Sample 1** for experimental analysis.

Sample 1:
size ~ 0.05 - 1.0 mm

Sample 2:
Grain size <0.05 mm

FIGURE 1: PICTURES OF SHREDDED PV SAMPLE 1 (A) AND SAMPLE 2 (B), DISPLAYING DIFFERENT GRAIN SIZES, RECEIVED FROM CSP.

3.1.2 Reagents and Solvent Preparation

Concentrated HNO₃, Ethaline (Choline Chloride (ChCl): Ethylene Glycol (EG), 1:1), Brine (ChCl: H₂O, 1:1), FeCl₃, CuCl₂. Chemicals procured have been used without any further purification. Deionized (DI) water was obtained from Elga Purelab Option. The DES – Ethaline (ChCl:EG, 1:1) and Brine (ChCl:H₂O, 1:1), were synthesized by mixing their appropriate proportions at 60° C to obtain a clear homogenous liquid. These were further utilized for preparing 0.5 M FeCl₃ and CuCl₂ redox catalyst solutions by heating and stirring at 60° C.

3.1.3 Electrodes

Pt disk (working electrode), Ag wire (counter electrode), Pt flag (reference electrode).

3.1.4 Instrumentation

The study utilized shredded PV samples labelled **APOLLO_A31_CSP_01-02-24**. The materials were subjected to various stages of analysis and processing, employing advanced equipment including Quanta 650 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (**FE-SEM**) equipped with Energy Dispersive X-ray (**EDX**) and Aztec Software for identifying the types of metals present in the sample, Thermo Scientific iCAP-Qc Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (**ICP-MS**), Deep Decomposition and Deconvolution Microscopy (**3DM**), and an **IVIUMnSTAT Potentiostat**. The sonicated experiments were conducted using CL-334 Q700 **sonicator** with an operating frequency of 20kHz and power output of 700 W. The combination of FE-SEM with EDX provides a high-resolution imaging platform for morphological analysis while simultaneously identifying elemental compositions. ICP-MS complements this by allowing quantification of trace metals with high sensitivity, which is critical for assessing recycling potential.

ICP-MS Procedure: For ICP-MS analysis, 5 g of shredded samples were digested in 50 ml of concentrated HNO_3 at 60°C for approximately 24 hours. The resulting solution was filtered, and 10 ml of this filtrate was diluted with 25 ml of deionized (DI) water in a volumetric flask. This diluted solution was passed through a 0.32-micron PET (polyethylene terephthalate) syringe filter and transferred into a vial for ICP analysis. A blank solution was prepared following the same procedure.

SEM and 3DM Analysis: For SEM analysis, the shredded samples were directly mounted on carbon tape, while 3DM was employed for detailed imaging on thin glass plates.

Potentiostat Configuration: IVIUMnSTAT Potentiostat is configured with Pt disk (0.5mm diameter) as the working electrode, Ag wire as the reference electrode, and Pt flag as the counter electrode in a three-cell setup. The working electrode carefully polished every time before running the experiment, for about 3-4 mins using $0.3\ \mu\text{m}$ and $0.05\ \mu\text{m}$ alumina slurry, and then rinsed with DI water and air dried.

3.2 Initial Assessment for Elemental Composition Analysis:

FIGURE 2: EDX ELEMENTAL MAPPING IMAGES FOR DETERMINING ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION OF THE SHREDDED PV SAMPLE 1.

The experimental process began with determining the morphology of the samples and performing elemental composition analysis on shredded silicon sand of two different grain sizes (*Sample 1 and Sample 2*), provided by CSP, as shown in **Figure 1 (a) and (b)**.

TABLE 1: ICP-MS ANALYSIS OF THE SAMPLE 1.

Sample Elements	Sample 1 [%]	Sample 2 [%]
Al	5.27	4.7
Mg	0.04	0.03
Ca	0.07	0.08
Cu	2.99	2.72
Ag	1.608	1.312
Sn	0.16	0.3
Pb	0.27	0.23
Bi	0.027	0.05
Mg	0.4	0.03

Preliminary tests for identifying metals types were conducted on both samples, using the ICP-MS, confirming that the shredded PV samples contained approximately 1.6% Ag (**Table 1**) in Sample 1 and 1.3% Ag in Sample 2, along with the presence of other metals and their respective compositions. Further analysis was continued with Sample 1 only, as it exhibited a higher Ag concentration compared to Sample 2. The EDX elemental mapping of Sample 1 revealed the heterogenous distribution of Ag, Cu and Al element (**Figure 2**) and their detailed weight percentage composition is presented in **Table 2** with a total of 6 reports at different positions (numbered as 1 to 6 in Table 2) so as to have a better understanding of the distribution of elements within the Sample 1, and the collective summary of the elements has been presented in table below.

FIGURE 3: 3DM MICROSCOPE IMAGES OF SAMPLE 1 SHOWING NON-HOMOGENOUS BEHAVIOUR

The 3DM highlighted the polycrystalline and non-homogeneous nature of the samples with the presence of Ag tracks (vide **Figure 3(b) and 3(c)**), crushed glass particles (vide **Figure 3(e) and 3(f)**), and evidence of metal leaching (vide **Figure 3(d)**).

TABLE 2: EDX REPORT OF THE SAMPLE 1.

Report No	Al [wt%]	Ag [wt%]	Cu [wt%]	Ca [wt%]	Na [wt%]	Si [wt%]
1	36.4	3.09	0	0.7	0	59.7
2	10.7	9.31	9.3	0	1.08	69.6
3	10.98	8.94	10.13	0	1.09	68.8
4	25	0	0	0.72	0	74.1
5	17.2	2.26	18.36	2.28	0	59.44
6	21.6	1.77	1.8	2.6	4.3	68.08

3.3 Etching Process with Stirring

Following the elemental analysis, efforts were made to evaluate the – (i) Efficiency of the oxidising agents and the DES media during the etching process with stirring, (ii) Determining effective extraction procedures for Ag, and (iii) Assessing the time required for complete Ag etching from Sample 1.

(i) To investigate the efficiency of the etching process, a leaching experiment was performed by stirring 10 grams of the shredded samples separately with Ethaline and Brine (50 ml) at temperature between 60°C-65°C with continuous stirring for one hour, as outlined in the following **Scheme 1**.

SCHEME 1: METHODOLOGY FOR SEPARATING THE TCMs (PRIMARILY AG EXTRACTION) WITH STIRRING FROM SAMPLE 1.

This experiment resulted in the formation of *two distinct phases* - an *unreacted solid residue* and a *filtrate*, which was expected to contain the leached Ag, and later both phases have been analysed. The unreacted solid residue was analysed using EDX to assess the remaining TCM content (**Figure 4**). On the other hand, the filtrate was further processed and analysed using Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) to confirm the presence of Ag and to optimize its recovery process, outlined in **Figure 5**.

FIGURE 4: FESEM IMAGES OF THE UNREACTED SOLID RESIDUE AFTER THE ETCHING EXPERIMENT.

EDX analysis of the *residue* confirmed that there is **no Ag content**, with results indicating the effective etching of Ag into the filtrate (**Figure 4**). And therefore, experiment demonstrated the ability of the DES media (Ethaline and Brine) to efficiently dissolve Ag into the filtrate. This highlights the method's potential for environmentally friendly and economically viable Ag extraction from PV waste.

Following this, the filtrate was analysed using CV to detect the presence of Ag ions and optimize the recovery process. Ag detection was enhanced using a **stripping CV technique**. (as low Ag concentration in sample resulted in appearance of smaller Ag redox couple in CV and thereby it becomes difficult to recognize)

For Stripping Cyclic voltammetry, scans were conducted on 5 grams of Sample 1 leached with FeCl_3 in brine, at a scan rate of 20mV/s, within the potential window of -0.3 V to +0.6 V, as shown in **Figure 5 (a) and (c)**.

FIGURE 5: CV GRAPHS OF THE SAMPLE 1 AFTER THE ETCHING OF 5G OF SAMPLE 1 WITH FeCl_3 IN BRINE AND FeCl_3 IN ETHALINE, WITH AND WITHOUT STRIPPING FOR ABOUT 1 MIN.

During the measurement, a stripping procedure was also employed by pausing the scan at -0.3 V for approximately 3 mins, followed by resumption of the scan. This step allowed the accumulation of Ag ions near the electrode surface in the solution, thereby enhancing their detection. As a result, the peak height of $\text{Ag}^0/\text{Ag}^{+1}$ couple in the current voltage graph effect was significantly increased (see **Figure 5 (b) and (d)**). The result confirmed that the FeCl_3 in brine effectively dissolved and transferred Ag ions into the leachate during the reaction. For clarity, only the FeCl_3 results have been presented in this report, though other DES media (mentioned earlier in report) have also clearly demonstrated the Ag peaks during stripping CV analysis.

(ii) After confirming the leaching of Ag by DES (Deep Eutectic Solvents), preliminary experiments were conducted to extract Ag from the leachate - FeCl_3 in Ethaline, using three different approaches, with the purpose to identify the most effective recovery process for Ag ions: -

A. Fe Cementation:

This cost-effective method relies on a redox reaction, where iron (Fe), being more electropositive, displaces silver ions from the solution. Due to the electrochemical potential difference between Fe and Ag, Ag ions are reduced to metallic Ag and deposited on the Fe wire. The process requires no external energy and occurs spontaneously under ambient conditions.

Procedure: Fe wire was immersed in the leachate for 1-2 hours (see **Figure 6(a) and 6(b)**).

Outcome: The deposited Ag on Fe wire was collected and later analysed using EDX which confirmed the presence of Ag.

Explanation: $\text{Fe (s)} + 2\text{AgCl (aq)} \rightarrow \text{FeCl}_2 \text{ (aq)} + 2\text{Ag (s)}$

Here, Iron (Fe) displaces silver (Ag) from silver chloride (AgCl), causing silver metal (Ag) to precipitate out of solution and deposit on the iron surface. Iron (Fe) becomes Fe^{2+} ions in the solution, forming FeCl_2 . Thus, Fe cementation is a chemical displacement process where one metal displaces another metal.

FIGURE 6: FE CEMENTATION FOR EXTRACTION OF AG FROM FeCl_3 ETHALINE LEACHATE OF THE SAMPLE 1.

B. Galvanic Deposition:

This method employs a sacrificial metal, such as copper (Cu), to induce the deposition of Ag via galvanic coupling. The process is driven by the potential difference between Cu and Ag, leading to the reduction of Ag ions onto the Cu surface (**Figure 7(a)**).

FIGURE 7: AG EXTRACTION ON (A) THICK CU PLATE BY GALVANIC DEPOSITION AND (B) ON BRASS PLATE BY ELECTRODEPOSITION

Procedure: A Cu electrode was immersed in the leachate ().

Outcome: Ag deposition was observed on the Cu surface.

Explanation: $\text{Cu (s)} + 2\text{Ag}^+(\text{aq}) \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+}(\text{aq}) + 2\text{Ag (s)}$

Copper (Cu) reacts with silver ions (Ag^+) in the solution, where copper is oxidized to Cu^{2+} , and silver is reduced and deposited as solid Ag on the cathode. Therefore, this galvanic deposition process is an electrochemical process where metal ions are reduced spontaneously.

C. Electrodeposition:

Electrodeposition uses an external electric current to reduce Ag ions onto an inert electrode. A two-electrode system was employed, with a brass electrode as the working electrode (expected Ag deposition site) and a platinum (Pt) mesh as the counter electrode.

Procedure: A controlled potential was applied to drive the reduction of Ag from the DES solution onto the brass surface (see **Figure 7(b)**).

Outcome: Preliminary results indicated Ag deposition, but further optimization is needed for enhanced efficiency.

The experimental results demonstrated the feasibility of using DES solvents for extracting silver from shredded PV modules. Out of above 3 procedures, the Fe cementation was found to be working more effectively and, other two methods need to be further optimized for efficient Ag recovery.

Finally, (iii) the optimization of the reaction time to fully etch the silver from Sample 1 was performed, as described in the next section of this report.

3.4 Time Analysis Study of Etching with Stirring

To determine the optimal etching duration for Ag, a **time-based study** of the DES process was conducted by etching process described in previous section with stirring. The experiment involved 100 mL of 0.5 M FeCl₃ or CuCl₂ in a brine solution, with 10 g of the shredded PV sample and reaction is performed at 65°C. Unlike the previous experiment, the etching reaction was monitored by sampling at intervals of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 minutes (instead of continuing for a period of an hour), followed by regular 10-minute intervals up to 60 minutes (see Scheme 2).

SCHEME 2: SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF THE TIME ANALYSIS STUDY OF THE SAMPLE 1 BY ETCHING WITH STIRRING.

For each interval, CV was performed to analyse the Ag peak height, allowing the identification of the time corresponding to maximum Ag extraction. The results for FeCl₃ in Brine DES are provided in Figure 8 below.

FIGURE 8: OVERLAY OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMOGRAM OF ETCHING PROCESS OF FeCl₃ BRINE DES FOR SAMPLE 1 WITH STIRRING, (A)

FOR ALL THE TIME INTERVALS AND (B) FOR 10, 20, 30 AND 40 MIN INTERVALS ONLY. IN FIGURE (A) AND (B) TA1-FB REPRESENTS TIME ANALYSIS EXPERIMENT PERFORMED ON SAMPLE 1 BY ETCHING WITH STIRRING OF FeCl₃ IN BRINE DES.

The overlaid CV measurement for FeCl_3 in Brine shows three redox peaks— $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$, Ag^0/Ag^+ and Cu^0/Cu^+ redox couples as displayed in **Figure 8(a)**. However, due to overlapping peaks, identifying the exact position of the Ag^0/Ag^+ peak is challenging. To resolve this ambiguity, **Figure 8(b)** displays the CV graph for selected time intervals (10, 20, 30, and 40 minutes), where the change in Ag^0/Ag^+ peak height is clearer. A 3D representation of the CV data (**Figure 9(a)**) further illustrates the progression of the reaction, confirming that the etching reaction reaches completion at approximately **40 minutes**. This observation is supported by **Figure 9(b)**, which plots the time intervals against the anodic peak current height for Ag, showing a maximum value around 40 minutes.

FIGURE 9: (A) 3D REPRESENTATION OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMOGRAM OF ETCHING PROCESS WITH STIRRING BY USING FeCl_3 IN BRINE DES OF SAMPLE 1 FOR ALL THE INTERVALS AND (B) PLOT OF ANODIC PEAK CURRENT HEIGHT FOR AG VS TIME INTERVALS.

FIGURE 10: OVERLAY OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMOGRAM OF ETCHING PROCESS OF CuCl_2 BRINE DES FOR SAMPLE 1 WITH STIRRING, (A) FOR ALL THE INTERVALS AND (B) FOR THE 10, 20, 30 AND 40 MIN INTERVALS ONLY. IN FIGURE (A) AND (B) TA1-FB REPRESENTS TIME ANALYSIS EXPERIMENT PERFORMED ON SAMPLE 1 BY ETCHING WITH STIRRING OF CuCl_2 IN BRINE DES.

Similar experiment was performed with the CuCl_2 DES media, which also exhibited three peaks – $\text{Cu}^{+1}/\text{Cu}^{+2}$, $\text{Ag}^0/\text{Ag}^{+1}$ and $\text{Cu}^0/\text{Cu}^{+1}$ redox couples as outlined in **Figure 10 (a)**. To clarify the data, **Figure 10(b)** provides the CV graph for selected intervals. 3D analysis of the CV data (**Figure 11(a)**) reveals that the reaction requires 60 minutes for complete etching, as supported by the time vs. anodic peak current plot in **Figure 11(b)**. These results indicate that **CuCl_2 in brine DES** requires a **longer time** (60 minutes) to etch **Ag** compared to **FeCl_3 in brine DES** (40 minutes).

FIGURE 11: (A) 3D REPRESENTATION OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMOGRAM OF ETCHING PROCESS WITH STIRRING WITH CuCl_2 BRINE DES OF SAMPLE 1 FOR ALL THE INTERVALS AND (B) PLOT OF ANODIC PEAK CURRENT HEIGHT FOR AG VS TIME INTERVALS.

3.5 Ultrasonication Assisted Etching with Stirring

Ultrasonication, the application of high-frequency sound waves, induces significant physical, chemical, and mechanical effects that enhance etching efficiency, surface modification, and dissolution processes. These effects play a crucial role in improving the precision and effectiveness of material removal in chemical etching applications.

The cavitation effects generated by alternating high-pressure and low-pressure cycles in the liquid medium during ultrasonication lead to the formation and subsequent collapse of microscopic gas bubbles. This process enhances the penetration of the etchant into fine structures, ensuring deeper and more uniform material removal. Additionally, ultrasonication disrupts stagnant boundary layers near the sample surface, which are typically formed during conventional stirring, thereby ensuring continuous replenishment of the etchant.

The microjets and high-energy shock waves produced during cavitation create a more homogeneous etching environment, minimizing variations in etching rates across the sample surface. Given these advantages, ultrasonication assisted etching with stirring was compared with conventional etching process with stirring

only, to evaluate their relative effectiveness through time-analysis experiments (time required to etch Ag), as outlined in the APOLLO Project plan.

To assess the impact of ultrasonication on etching efficiency, in-situ experiments were conducted using cyclic voltammetry (CV) while applying ultrasound followed by stirring. The experiments were performed on the Sample 1 using FeCl_3 and CuCl_2 in both brine and ethaline media. For reference, the results for 0.5 M FeCl_3 in brine and 0.5 M CuCl_2 in ethaline at a scan rate of 50mV/s, are given in **Figure 12 and 13**.

FIGURE 12: OVERLAY OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMOGRAM OF ETCHING PROCESS OF FeCl_3 BRINE DES FOR SAMPLE 1 BY ULTRASONIC ASSISTED ETCHING PROCESS WITH STIRRING (A) FOR ALL THE INTERVALS AND (B) FOR INTERVALS 11, 14 AND 17 MINS. IN FIGURE (A) AND (B) TA1-FB REPRESENTS TIME ANALYSIS EXPERIMENT PERFORMED ON SAMPLE 1 WITH FeCl_3 IN BRINE USING ULTRASONIC ASSISTED ETCHING.

Figure 12(a) and **Figure 13(a)** show CV scans for different time intervals. Due to the shorter potential window used, only *two redox couples* are visible. To clarify the Ag peak height, **Figures 12(b) and 13(b)** present CV graphs for three selected time intervals. Though, the exact time calculation for completion of etching was clear when area under the Ag redox peak were plotted against the time, as shown in **Figure 14 (a) and (b)** for FeCl_3 in brine and CuCl_2 in ethaline respectively. From **Figure 14 (a) and (b)**, it can be claimed that leaching process with Ultra-sonification requires only 17 mins with FeCl_3 in brine while CuCl_2 in ethaline requires only 9 mins for the same.

Therefore, the Ultra sonification process has been found to be effective in reducing the leaching time for extracting Ag from the DES medium to a greater extent.

FIGURE 14: OVERLAY OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMOGRAM OF ETCHING PROCESS OF CUCL₂ ETHALINE DES FOR SAMPLE 1 BY ULTRASONIC ASSISTED ETCHING WITH STIRRING PROCESS (A) FOR ALL THE INTERVALS AND (B) FOR THE INTERVALS 0, 5 AND 8 MINS ONLY. IN FIGURE (A) AND (B) TA1-CB REPRESENTS TIME ANALYSIS EXPERIMENT PERFORMED ON CUCL₂ IN ETHALINE DES USING ULTRASOUND ASSISTED STIRRING.

FIGURE 13: PLOT OF ANODIC PEAK CURRENT HEIGHT FOR AG VS TIME INTERVALS FOR (A) FeCl₃ IN BRINE (B) CUCL₂ IN ETHALINE DES FOR ULTRASONIC ASSISTED ETCHING PROCESS.

Key Observations includes:

Ultrasonication-assisted etching reduced the leaching time to:

1. 17 minutes for FeCl₃ in brine from 40 min without Ultrasound.
2. 9 minutes for CuCl₂ in Ethaline from 60 min without Ultrasound.

4. Conclusion

This project has provided significant insights into the etching behaviour of Ag in redox catalysts- deep eutectic solvent (DES) combination using stirring without ultrasound and stirring with ultrasonic - assisted agitation and their confirmation by cyclic voltammetry (CV) analysis. Through systematic experiments, we have successfully established a methodology for determining Ag^+ concentrations in the etching solution and have also tried to confirm its presence after leaching in the leachate.

The findings from this study will be instrumental in shaping the upcoming milestones and deliverables of the project:

Optimized Etching Process: The results contribute to refining the etching parameters like time, which will be crucial for developing efficient and controlled material processing techniques in future work packages.

Integration into Sonification Studies (D2.2):

The comparative analysis between ultrasound and stirring without ultrasound has provided valuable data for Deliverable D2.2. This helps demonstrate that ultrasonication enhances both etching efficiency and selectivity. For example, with CuCl_2 in Ethaline, ultrasonication reduced the leaching time from 60 minutes to just 9 minutes, while for FeCl_3 in brine, it was reduced from 40 minutes to 17 minutes. In other words, ultrasonication halved the etching time for FeCl_3 and reduced it by a factor of 1/7 for CuCl_2 .

These results demonstrate that ultrasonication significantly enhances the efficiency of Ag extraction, making it a highly effective alternative to conventional stirring.

The project has also addressed practical implementation challenges, including the reproducibility of DES media with electrochemical measurements. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of metal dissolution mechanisms in alternative green solvents, paving the way for sustainable and efficient processing techniques in material science applications. Further work will focus on refining these methodologies and exploring their broader applicability to other metal systems.

